

EXAMINING FACTORS INFLUENCING THE ADOPTION OF CHATGPT AMONG LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE FACULTY MEMBERS IN PAKISTAN

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Abstract

This study investigates the factors influencing the adoption of ChatGPT among Library and Information Science (LIS) faculty members in Pakistan, grounded in the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). A quantitative research design was employed, using a structured questionnaire distributed via email and WhatsApp to LIS faculty across public and private universities (N = 65). The study examined six major factors: ease of use, usefulness, social influence, innovativeness, facilitating conditions, and trustworthiness. Data were analyzed using SPSS, employing descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and simple linear regression techniques. Reliability analysis demonstrated strong internal consistency (composite $\alpha = .937$). The findings revealed that perceived usefulness, social influence, innovativeness, facilitating conditions, and trustworthiness significantly and positively predicted ChatGPT adoption, whereas ease of use did not show a significant effect. Results underscore that faculty members' willingness to adopt ChatGPT is primarily shaped by its perceived usefulness, supportive institutional conditions, and trust in the technology. The study recommends that universities enhance AI-related training, ensure robust digital infrastructure, and develop ethical guidelines to strengthen trust and effective utilization of ChatGPT in academia.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to the ability of a computer program to learn, reason, and perform tasks that would typically require human intelligence (Mitchell, 2019). It involves modeling human cognitive processes using computer systems (Limna et al., 2022). AI systems are designed to solve problems, make decisions, and carry out actions with varying levels of human supervision (Gil de Zúñiga et al., 2024). One of the most transformative applications of AI in recent years is ChatGPT, a conversational AI model developed by OpenAI, which uses natural language processing to interact with users in a human-like manner (Sakib, 2023; Zhai, 2022).

The introduction of ChatGPT in November 2022 marked a significant technological advancement. Within just two months, it reached 100 million users, making it the fastest-growing consumer application in history (Lampropoulos et al., 2025). Trained on a vast corpus of data, ChatGPT can produce coherent and contextually relevant responses, making it useful in various sectors, including education (Sakib, 2023; Zhai, 2022). In educational settings, ChatGPT offers personalized learning, supports lesson planning, and enhances content creation across disciplines (Kevin Fuchs, 2023; Vasconcelos et al., 2023). It functions as a virtual assistant, tutor, and collaborative tool (Sridhar et al., 2022; Sreenivasu et al., 2023).

However, despite these benefits, the adoption of ChatGPT in academia, especially among Library and Information Science (LIS) faculty, raises important considerations. Faculty members have expressed concerns about the credibility, accuracy, and trustworthiness of AI-generated content (Al-Mughairi & Bhaskar, 2024). There are also ethical concerns regarding AI-assisted cheating and data privacy (Al-Mughairi & Bhaskar, 2024). Trust plays a foundational role in AI adoption within education, as users must rely on AI systems for critical academic tasks (Almogren et al., 2024). Ensuring the consistent delivery of reliable and accurate information is therefore essential for faculty acceptance.

Understanding faculty attitudes and factors influencing ChatGPT adoption is crucial. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), proposed by Davis (1989), offers a strong framework for evaluating these factors. TAM posits that perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use are primary drivers of technology adoption. When users perceive a tool as useful and easy to operate, their intention to adopt it increases (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000; Wang et

al., 2023). In recent studies, these dimensions have been reaffirmed as significant predictors of ChatGPT usage (Al-kfairy, 2024).

Additional factors, such as social influence (the role of peers and professional networks), *user innovativeness* (openness to trying new technologies), and facilitating conditions (availability of resources and institutional support), have also been shown to impact AI adoption (Liu & Tao, 2022). Trust, specifically perceived trustworthiness, has emerged as a vital element in influencing whether users feel confident in adopting AI tools in high-stakes contexts like education (Al-Mughairi & Bhaskar, 2024; Almogren et al., 2024). Cultural and contextual factors, such as communication styles, language preferences, and societal norms, also shape attitudes toward AI use (Kuang et al., 2023; Stahl & Eke, 2024). These nuances are particularly relevant in academic environments where critical evaluation and contextual understanding are integral to faculty roles.

This study focuses on Library and Information Science faculty members, aiming to explore their attitudes toward ChatGPT and identify the key factors influencing its adoption. Understanding their perspectives is important, given their unique role in supporting learning, research, and information literacy in educational institutions. By applying the TAM framework, this study seeks to assess the impact of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, social influence, user innovativeness, facilitating conditions, and trustworthiness on the adoption of ChatGPT among LIS faculty. These insights will help educational institutions develop better support systems and adoption strategies that align with faculty expectations and concerns.

Statement of the Problem

The growing use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies in education, especially tools like ChatGPT, has introduced new opportunities and challenges for academic professionals. Among the key factors influencing adoption is effort expectancy, which refers to how easy or difficult users believe it is to use a system. If faculty members perceive ChatGPT as complex or requiring excessive effort, they are less likely to adopt it (Enholtm, 2022). Conversely, when the technology is perceived as user-friendly, intuitive, and requiring minimal technical skill, its adoption becomes more likely. In addition to effort expectancy, concerns about data privacy *and* security have become increasingly significant in educational environments, where sensitive information may be shared or generated by AI systems (Al-Mughairi & Bhaskar, 2024).

A variety of other factors also influence the intention to adopt AI tools like ChatGPT. These include performance expectancy, perceived usefulness, facilitating conditions, social influence, trust, and individual traits such as innovativeness and prior experience (Al-Nuaimi, 2022; Liu & Tao, 2022). Attitudes toward ChatGPT, particularly how useful and easy it is perceived to be, play a critical role in adoption (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000). While much attention has been given to the use of AI in general, there is a notable gap in understanding how faculty in Library and Information Science, who play a key role in shaping digital practices in education perceive and adopt these tools.

This study aims to address this gap by applying the Technology Acceptance Model to explore the behavioral, technological, and contextual factors affecting ChatGPT adoption among LIS faculty in Pakistan. Despite being in a field that promotes information literacy and emerging technologies, LIS faculty members' attitudes and trust in tools like ChatGPT remain underexplored. By empirically examining these factors, the study will provide insights into the conditions under which LIS faculty are likely to adopt ChatGPT. The findings will help inform effective strategies for integrating AI in academic environments and support the broader digital transformation of higher education.

Research Question

1. What are the factors influencing the adoption of ChatGPT among LIS faculty members?

Theoretical Support and Conceptual Framework

The Technology Acceptance Model, originally developed by Fred Davis in 1989, has become one of the most influential frameworks for studying technology adoption and user acceptance. For over two decades, TAM has provided theoretical support for understanding how users come to accept and use new technologies. It proposes that two key beliefs, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use serve as fundamental determinants of users' attitudes toward technology and ultimately influence their behavioral intentions and actual usage (Marangunić & Granić, 2015).

As an intention-based model, TAM is particularly valuable for explaining and predicting individuals' acceptance of computer-based technologies across various contexts, including education (Hu et al., 1999). Perceived usefulness refers to the extent to which a user believes that using a particular system would enhance their job or academic performance. In

contrast, perceived ease of use reflects the degree to which the user believes that the technology will be free of effort and simple to operate (Masrom, 2007).

In the context of this study, TAM offers a relevant and robust framework to examine the adoption of ChatGPT among Library and Information Science (LIS) faculty members. By integrating TAM with additional constructs such as social influence, facilitating conditions, trust, and user innovativeness, the conceptual framework of this study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the behavioral, technological, and contextual factors that influence the intention to use and actual adoption of ChatGPT in academic settings.

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis Development

Based on the above conceptual framework researcher has to make the following hypotheses:

H1: Perceived ease of use has a significant positive effect on the adoption of ChatGPT

H2: Perceived usefulness has a significant positive effect on the adoption of ChatGPT.

H3: Social influence has a significant positive effect on the adoption of ChatGPT.

H4: User innovativeness positively effect the adoption of ChatGPT.

H5: Facilitating conditions have significant positive effects on the adoption of ChatGPT.

H6: Perceived trustworthiness significantly positively effect the adoption of ChatGPT.

Literature Review

The integration of generative artificial intelligence tools such as ChatGPT into higher education has attracted growing scholarly attention, with researchers exploring adoption factors through established frameworks like the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT/UTAUT2), and Innovation Resistance Theory (IRT). Empirical studies highlight a complex interplay of technological, psychological, and contextual determinants that shape students' and educators' willingness to adopt AI in teaching, learning, and research environments.

Alghamdi and Alhasawi (2024) surveyed 340 university students in the United States using IRT and found that six barriers, usage, value, risk, tradition, image, and perceived cost, significantly and negatively influenced intention to adopt ChatGPT. These barriers captured perceptions of complexity, lack of value, privacy risks, resistance to change, negative image, and affordability concerns. A qualitative perspective from Al-Mughairi and Bhaskar (2024), who conducted in-depth interviews with 34 Omani faculty members, reinforced these findings by highlighting barriers such as reduced human interaction, lack of institutional support, job insecurity, and reliability issues alongside privacy concerns. Together, these studies underscore that resistance to ChatGPT adoption is not only technological but also systemic and socio-cultural, requiring institutional policies and support mechanisms.

Shahzad et al. (2025), in a survey of 368 Pakistani students, reported that trust mediated the relationship between self-efficacy and actual use, while perceived usefulness and ease of use moderated trust, underscoring the central role of confidence-building in AI systems. Similarly, Almogren et al. (2024) analyzed data from 458 university students and found perceived ease of use and usefulness as strong predictors of adoption intention. Their extension of TAM introduced trialability, compatibility, feedback quality, and assessment quality, which positively influenced ease of use and attitudes, though trust and subjective norms had limited effects. Almulla (2024) added a collaborative learning perspective, demonstrating that interactive and collaborative learning, along with information quality, influenced ease of use and usefulness, which mediated learning satisfaction. Interestingly, ChatGPT use did not directly predict satisfaction, indicating that intermediate variables such

as engagement and content quality might play stronger roles. Maheshwar (2024), integrating TAM with the Theory of Planned Behavior in Vietnam, found ease of use strongly influenced both usefulness and adoption intention, but usefulness itself did not directly predict intention. Instead, it affected adoption indirectly through personalization and interactivity, pointing to the importance of customization and user engagement in emerging technological contexts.

UTAUT and UTAUT2 frameworks have also been applied to explore adoption in different populations. Hasan Emon et al. (2024) modified UTAUT2 to examine Bangladeshi professionals and showed that performance expectancy, facilitating conditions, trust, and attitude toward AI significantly predicted adoption, while effort expectancy had a negative impact. This suggests that even when benefits are acknowledged, usability challenges can still hinder adoption. Subhani et al. (2025) applied UTAUT2 among Pakistani students and revealed that performance expectancy, hedonic motivation, self-efficacy, and habit positively predicted adoption intention, while price value and facilitating conditions had negligible or negative effects. Academic integrity was found to moderate the link between intention and actual use, underscoring ethical considerations as a key component in the adoption of generative AI in higher education.

Cambra-Fierro et al. (2025), studying Spanish faculty, found that perceived usefulness, ease of use, and enjoyment not only predicted adoption but also improved well-being by enhancing happiness and energy while reducing stress. Their findings suggest that adoption is shaped not only by utilitarian but also by affective considerations. Moghavvemi and Jam (2025), focusing on Malaysian students' continued use of ChatGPT, reported that perceived value mediated the relationship between usefulness, information quality, problem-solving ability, and creativity support with continuous usage intention. However, privacy concerns moderated adoption, reducing long-term engagement despite high perceived benefits. These results indicate that sustained adoption depends on balancing functional value with trust and data security.

Gude (2025) studied 219 U.S. students and found that age and gender shaped trust in ChatGPT, and that students accustomed to using Google were more likely to adopt AI tools for product research, while those relying on personal networks were less likely. Although trust initially appeared significant, it lost explanatory power in regression analyses when combined with behavioral variables, suggesting it operates indirectly or in interaction with other factors.

Expanding on demographic and contextual variables, Howlader et al. (2025) analyzed 729 Bangladeshi students across public and private universities and found that perceived usefulness ($\beta = 0.42$, $p < .001$ in private; $\beta = 0.41$ in public) and ease of use ($\beta = 0.32$, $p < .001$ in private; $\beta = 0.31$ in public) significantly predicted adoption, while perceived risk negatively influenced adoption ($\beta = -0.35$, $p < .001$ in private; $\beta = -0.31$ in public). The model explained substantial variance (53% in private universities, 48% in public) and demonstrated strong reliability and fit indices (CFI = 0.904, RMSEA = 0.045, Cronbach's $\alpha > .79$). These findings confirm the enduring significance of usefulness, ease of use, and risk as adoption predictors while highlighting differences across institutional contexts.

Al-kaifery (2024) conducted a narrative review and noted that most studies employed cross-sectional surveys, with analytical methods such as PLS-SEM dominating, though advanced approaches like artificial neural networks and deep neural networks were also used. Key factors consistently reported included usefulness, ease of use, trust, cost, and institutional support. However, the review emphasized that demographic variables, privacy, and facilitating conditions showed inconsistent effects across contexts, pointing to the need for more longitudinal and context-sensitive research designs. The review further suggested integrating psychological and contextual constructs into adoption models to capture the complexity of ChatGPT adoption in educational environments.

Taken together, the empirical evidence demonstrates that ChatGPT adoption in higher education is influenced by a multifaceted set of variables spanning technical, psychological, emotional, contextual, and institutional domains. Foundational models such as TAM and UTAUT2 continue to provide robust explanatory frameworks, yet extensions incorporating collaborative learning, affective well-being, and ethical considerations have enriched the literature. Perceived usefulness and ease of use consistently emerge as central predictors across contexts, but adoption is often hindered by risks related to privacy, institutional support, and social perceptions. Furthermore, emotional well-being, engagement, and integrity considerations highlight that adoption outcomes extend beyond mere utility. These findings suggest that for policymakers, educators, and developers to foster responsible and meaningful integration of ChatGPT, adoption strategies must move beyond technical performance to address trust, institutional policies, ethical frameworks, and user-centered design.

Methodology

The researchers conducted a comprehensive review of the relevant literature on the factors influencing the adoption of ChatGPT among Library and Information Science (LIS) faculty members in Pakistan. Guided by the methodological trends observed in previous studies (Maheshwar 2024; Subhani et al., 2025; Shahzad et al., 2025), a quantitative research design was employed to address the research questions effectively. This approach was chosen because it allows for objective measurement and statistical analysis of relationships among variables, ensuring consistency with earlier empirical investigations in the field.

Population

Since the total population of Library and Information Science (LIS) faculty members in Pakistan could not be precisely determined due to the absence of an official database, the study employed an accessible population approach. The respondents were full-time LIS faculty members (N = 65) from public and private universities across Pakistan. Participants included individuals holding various academic ranks such as Lecturer, Assistant Professor, Associate Professor, and Professor.

Description and Development of Questionnaire

A structured questionnaire was developed on the basis of prior studies on the adoption and usage of ChatGPT (Alghamdi & Alhasawi, 2024; Shahzad et al., 2025; Al-Mughairi and Bhaskar, 2024). The instrument measured ease of use, usefulness, social influence, innovativeness, facilitating condition, trustworthiness, and adoption of ChatGPT. The statements were taken from relevant literature review to ensure contextual relevance, including Ease of use (Shahzad & Asif, 2025), usefulness, innovativeness, social influence, facilitating condition, and trustworthiness (Cambra et al., 2025; Subhani et al., 2025; Alghamdi & Alhasawi, 2024).

Data Collection Procedure

The questionnaire was shared via personal email and WhatsApp to the library and information science faculty members in Pakistan, both public and private universities. The responses of the 65 participants were coded in Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) for further analysis.

Measure(s)

Descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were used to analyze the data. Pearson correlation and simple linear regression analyses were conducted to examine factors influencing the adoption of ChatGPT among Library and Information Science faculty members in Pakistan, based on the Technology Acceptance Model. Cronbach’s alpha reliability analysis was conducted to assess the internal consistency of the measurement scales. As presented in Table 1, the reliability coefficients for *Ease of Use* ($\alpha = .902$), *Usefulness* ($\alpha = .858$), *Social Influence* ($\alpha = .881$), *Innovativeness* ($\alpha = .919$), *Trustworthiness* ($\alpha = .788$), and *Adoption of ChatGPT* ($\alpha = .892$) were all above the recommended threshold of .70, reflecting satisfactory to excellent reliability (Nunnally, 1978). The coefficient for *Facilitating Conditions* ($\alpha = .600$) was slightly below the acceptable level, suggesting moderate internal consistency; however, reliability values above .60 are still considered minimally acceptable in exploratory research (Gliner & Morgan, 2001; Mohamad et al., 2015). The overall composite reliability of the 36-item scale was $\alpha = .937$, demonstrating strong internal coherence and excellent measurement reliability.

Table 1.: Study variables, number of statements/items, and Cronbach’s alpha values.

Study variables	No of items	Cronbach’s alpha
Ease of Use	5	.902
Usefulness	5	.858
Social Influence	5	.881
Innovativeness	5	.919
Facilitating Conditions	5	.600
Trustworthiness	5	.788
Adoption of ChatGPT	6	.892
Composite Reliability	36	.937

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 2 summarizes the demographic characteristics of the respondents, including gender, educational level, designation, and type of institution. Most respondents were male (83.0%), and the majority held a PhD degree (74.3%). In terms of designation, nearly half were Assistant Professors (46.2%), followed by Lecturers (27.6%), Associate Professors (20.0%), and Professors

(6.2%). Most participants were affiliated with public universities (66.2%), while 33.8% were from private universities.

Table 2: Demographics of the Respondents

Variable	Frequency	%age
Gender		
Male	54	83.0
Female	11	17.0
Educational Level		
MS/M.PHIL	9	13.4
PHD	48	74.3
POSTDOC	8	13.3
Designation		
Lecturer	18	27.6
Assistant Professor	30	46.2
Associate Professor	13	20.0
Professor	4	6.2
Type of Institutions		
Public University	43	66.2
Private University	22	33.8
Total	65	100.0

Research Hypothesis Testing

To examine the proposed hypotheses regarding the adoption of ChatGPT among Library and Information Science faculty members, two statistical techniques were used: Pearson's correlation to test the strength and direction of relationships among variables, and simple linear regression to examine the predictive power of each independent variable on ChatGPT adoption. As shown in Table 3, the correlation analysis was conducted prior to hypothesis testing to confirm associations among the study constructs. The results indicated significant positive correlations among all major variables influencing the adoption of ChatGPT.

Table 3: Correlations Analysis

Variables	EOU	UFN	SI	IVN	FC	TWN	ACGPT
Ease of Use	1						
Usefulness	.043	1					
Social Influence	-.175	.388**	1				
Innovation	-.056	.877**	.911**	1			
Facilitating Conditions	-.087	.651**	.343**	.552**	1		
Trustworthiness	.095	.713**	.468**	.560**	.754**	1	
Adoption of ChatGPT	-.215	.519**	.572**	.696**	.645**	.578**	1

Note. N = 65. p < .01 (two-tailed).

The correlation matrix presented in Table 3 highlights strong, positive relationships among most study constructs, indicating that greater usefulness, innovativeness, facilitating conditions, and trust are associated with higher adoption of ChatGPT. These significant correlations provide sufficient justification for conducting regression analyses, as reported in Table 4.

Table 4: Regression Analysis

Statistic	Ease of Use	Usefulness	Social Influence	Innovation	Facilitating Conditions	Trustworthiness
R	.215	.519	.572	.696	.645	.578
R ²	.046	.269	.327	.485	.416	.334
Adjusted R ²	.031	.257	.317	.476	.406	.323
F-Value	3.07	23.18	30.64	54.61	44.80	29.11
Sig. (F-test)	.085	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
B	-0.17	0.64	0.47	0.58	0.70	0.53
(Unstandardized Coefficient)						
Std. Error (B)	0.10	0.13	0.09	0.08	0.10	0.10
β (Standardized Beta)	-0.22	0.52	0.57	0.70	0.65	0.58
t-value	-1.75	4.82	5.54	7.39	6.69	5.40
Sig. (t-test)	.085	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
95%	[-0.37,	[0.38, 0.91]	[0.30,	[0.42, 0.74]	[0.49, 0.90]	[0.34, 0.73]

Confidence Interval	0.03]			0.64]				
Results	H1	Not Supported	H2	Supported	H3	Supported	H4	Supported
							H5	Supported
								H6 Supported

To examine the factors influencing the adoption of ChatGPT among Library and Information Science (LIS) faculty members, Pearson correlation and simple linear regression analyses were conducted. The correlation analysis (Table 3) revealed significant positive relationships among most variables. Following this, regression analyses (Table 4) were performed to test the six hypotheses derived from the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM).

H1: Perceived ease of use has a significant positive effect on the adoption of ChatGPT.

The regression results indicated that perceived ease of use did not significantly predict the adoption of ChatGPT, $R = .215$, $R^2 = .046$, adjusted $R^2 = .031$, $F(1, 63) = 3.07$, $p = .085$. The regression coefficient was negative and nonsignificant ($B = -0.17$, $SE = 0.10$, $\beta = -.22$, $t(63) = -1.75$, $p = .085$, 95% CI [-0.37, 0.03]).

H2: Perceived usefulness has a significant positive effect on the adoption of ChatGPT.

Perceived usefulness significantly predicted the adoption of ChatGPT, $R = .519$, $R^2 = .269$, adjusted $R^2 = .257$, $F(1, 63) = 23.18$, $p < .001$. The coefficient was positive and significant ($B = 0.64$, $SE = 0.13$, $\beta = .52$, $t(63) = 4.82$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.38, 0.91]).

H3: Social influence has a significant positive effect on the adoption of ChatGPT.

Social influence also significantly predicted adoption, $R = .572$, $R^2 = .327$, adjusted $R^2 = .317$, $F(1, 63) = 30.64$, $p < .001$. The relationship was positive ($B = 0.47$, $SE = 0.09$, $\beta = .57$, $t(63) = 5.54$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.30, 0.64]).

H4: User innovativeness positively affects the adoption of ChatGPT.

User innovativeness showed a strong, significant positive influence on ChatGPT adoption, $R = .696$, $R^2 = .485$, adjusted $R^2 = .476$, $F(1, 63) = 54.61$, $p < .001$. The unstandardized coefficient was $B = 0.58$, $SE = 0.08$, $\beta = .70$, $t(63) = 7.39$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.42, 0.74].

H5: Facilitating conditions have a significant positive effect on the adoption of ChatGPT.

Facilitating conditions were a significant predictor of ChatGPT adoption, $R = .645$, $R^2 = .416$, adjusted $R^2 = .406$, $F(1, 63) = 44.80$, $p < .001$. The coefficient was positive and significant ($B = 0.70$, $SE = 0.10$, $\beta = .65$, $t(63) = 6.69$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.49, 0.90]).

H6: Perceived trustworthiness significantly positively affects the adoption of ChatGPT.

The results also showed that perceived trustworthiness significantly predicted adoption, $R = .578$, $R^2 = .334$, adjusted $R^2 = .323$, $F(1, 63) = 29.11$, $p < .001$. The coefficient was $B = 0.53$, $SE = 0.10$, $\beta = .58$, $t(63) = 5.40$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.34, 0.73].

Discussion

The study aimed to identify the key factors influencing the adoption of ChatGPT among Library and Information Science (LIS) faculty members by applying constructs derived from the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The findings from the regression analyses provide meaningful insights into how technological and psychological determinants shape faculty members' willingness to adopt generative AI tools.

Contrary to expectations, perceived ease of use did not significantly predict the adoption of ChatGPT, $R = .215$, $R^2 = .046$, $F(1, 63) = 3.07$, $p = .085$, with a nonsignificant and negative regression coefficient ($B = -0.17$, $\beta = -.22$, 95% CI [-0.37, 0.03]). This suggests that faculty members' adoption decisions may not depend solely on the simplicity of interacting with ChatGPT. This finding aligns with Alghamdi and Alhasawi (2024), who noted that users often resist AI tools despite usability advantages due to perceived risks and institutional constraints.

In contrast, perceived usefulness emerged as a significant predictor of ChatGPT adoption, $R = .519$, $R^2 = .269$, $F(1, 63) = 23.18$, $p < .001$, with a positive effect ($B = 0.64$, $\beta = .52$, 95% CI [0.38, 0.91]). This finding supports the core TAM proposition that usefulness drives technology acceptance (Almogren et al., 2024; Shahzad et al., 2025). Faculty members who perceived ChatGPT as beneficial for research, teaching, or content creation were more likely to adopt it, confirming that practical and performance-related benefits are central motivators for generative AI adoption.

Similarly, social influence (SI) significantly and positively predicted adoption, $R = .572$, $R^2 = .327$, $F(1, 63) = 30.64$, $p < .001$, with $B = 0.47$, $\beta = .57$, 95% CI [0.30, 0.64]. This suggests that recommendations, peer behaviors, and institutional norms strongly influence faculty decisions. These results are consistent with Subhani et al. (2025), who emphasized that peer acceptance and academic culture enhance intention to use AI tools in higher education.

User innovativeness was the strongest predictor among all variables, $R = .696$, $R^2 = .485$, $F(1, 63) = 54.61$, $p < .001$, with $B = 0.58$, $\beta = .70$, 95% CI [0.42, 0.74]. This finding indicates that

faculty members with a high tendency to explore and experiment with new technologies were more inclined to adopt ChatGPT. This result reinforces Maheshwar's (2024) conclusion that user innovation and experimentation enhance openness to adopting AI-driven platforms, particularly when they are perceived as novel and useful.

Facilitating conditions also demonstrated a strong positive effect, $R = .645$, $R^2 = .416$, $F(1, 63) = 44.80$, $p < .001$, $B = 0.70$, $\beta = .65$, 95% CI [0.49, 0.90]. This underscores the importance of access to technological infrastructure, institutional support, and adequate training for sustained use. These findings align with Hasan Emon et al. (2024) and Almulla (2024), who found that organizational and infrastructural readiness play a decisive role in facilitating the effective use of AI technologies in educational settings.

Finally, perceived trustworthiness significantly predicted adoption, $R = .578$, $R^2 = .334$, $F(1, 63) = 29.11$, $p < .001$, with $B = 0.53$, $\beta = .58$, 95% CI [0.34, 0.73]. Trust emerged as a fundamental component influencing faculty confidence in ChatGPT's reliability, accuracy, and ethical use. This supports Shahzad et al. (2025), who found that trust mediates the relationship between self-efficacy and actual use, reinforcing the necessity of ensuring data security and transparency in AI-driven educational technologies.

Overall, the results confirm that usefulness, social influence, innovativeness, facilitating conditions, and trustworthiness significantly shape ChatGPT adoption among LIS faculty, while ease of use alone does not. This suggests that experienced academic users prioritize functionality, reliability, and institutional readiness over mere ease of interaction. The findings highlight that successful AI adoption in academia requires a comprehensive strategy emphasizing not only technological efficiency but also institutional trust, training, and supportive environments.

Conclusion

The findings of this study provide important insights into the factors influencing the adoption of ChatGPT among Library and Information Science (LIS) faculty members. The results revealed that perceived usefulness, social influence, user innovativeness, facilitating conditions, and trustworthiness significantly predicted the adoption of ChatGPT, while perceived ease of use was not a significant determinant. This suggests that faculty members are more likely to adopt ChatGPT based on its perceived benefits, institutional and social support, and trust in the technology, rather than its simplicity or ease of operation. These findings indicate that

adoption behavior involves both technological and psychological dimensions, shaped by users' perceptions, institutional contexts, and willingness to innovate.

Overall, the study highlights that the successful integration of generative AI tools like ChatGPT in academic environments depends on fostering supportive conditions, building trust, and promoting innovative attitudes among educators. When faculty members view ChatGPT as a beneficial, reliable, and institutionally supported tool, they are more inclined to incorporate it into teaching, learning, and research activities. Universities should therefore focus on creating conducive environments that encourage ethical, responsible, and effective use of AI technologies to enhance academic performance and innovation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

- Universities and library administrations should strengthen institutional support and infrastructure by providing reliable internet access, AI-related training, and clear usage policies to promote effective ChatGPT adoption.
- Institutions should prioritize developing transparent policies on data privacy, security, and ethical use to enhance trust and minimize concerns regarding AI reliability.
- Faculty members should be encouraged to engage in creative and innovative uses of ChatGPT through academic incentives, workshops, and collaborative projects that foster experimentation.
- Training programs should focus on demonstrating the practical value and academic benefits of ChatGPT, emphasizing its role in improving productivity, research efficiency, and teaching effectiveness rather than solely highlighting ease of use.

Limitations of the Study

This study covers the factors effecting the adoption of ChatGPT among LIS faculty members in Pakistan. There are many factors that affect the adoption of ChatGPT, of which we will take a few. As the topic suggests, it only covers the adoption of one AI platform (ChatGPT), leaving the other platforms unaddressed. It only covers the attitude of LIS faculty members.

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Appendix-1

Factors Influencing the Adoption of ChatGPT

Please indicate your response to each item by selecting the option that best reflects your opinion or experience.

S. No	Statements	1	2	3	4	5
Ease of Use						
Scale: 1. Strongly Disagree, 2. Disagree, 3. Neutral, 4. Agree, 5. Strongly Agree						
1	I think using ChatGPT is easy.					
2	I believe that using ChatGPT only requires elementary abilities.					
3	It would be simple for me to access ChatGPT during my studies.					
4	I use ChatGPT because it makes it easier to find answers to inquiries and finish activities.					
5	I find the interaction with ChatGPT clear and understandable.					
Usefulness						
Scale: 1. Not Useful at All, 2. Slightly Useful, 3. Moderately Useful, 4. Very Useful, 5. Extremely Useful						
1	ChatGPT allows me to perform certain tasks more quickly.					
2	ChatGPT would increase my productivity.					
3	ChatGPT would improve my effectiveness.					
4	ChatGPT would enhance my performance as a teacher.					
5	Using ChatGPT can be helpful.					
Social Influence						
Scale: 1. Strongly Disagree, 2. Disagree, 3. Neutral, 4. Agree, 5. Strongly Agree						
1	Many people in my life believe that I ought to use ChatGPT.					
2	People who I respect in my life wants that I use ChatGPT.					

3	Those that shape my behavior think I have to use ChatGPT.					
4	Respected people in my life think using technology in insurance is a good thing.					
5	My colleagues encourage me to use ChatGPT in my academic work.					
Innovativeness						
Scale: 1. Not at all willing, 2. Slightly willing, 3. Moderately willing, 4. Very willing, 5. Extremely willing						
1	I am proud to be able to use ChatGPT in my classes.					
2	I look forward to going to work when I think about using ChatGPT.					
3	I am inspired by the potential use of ChatGPT for my classes.					
4	I feel empowered when I think about using ChatGPT.					
5	I feel energized when I consider using ChatGPT.					
Facilitating Condition						
Scale: 1. Strongly Disagree, 2. Disagree, 3. Neutral, 4. Agree, 5. Strongly Agree						
1	I possess the expertise required to utilize ChatGPT.					
2	ChatGPT is comparable to the technologies that I have already used.					
3	Training and guidance are available to help me learn how to use ChatGPT if I need it.					
4	My institution provides the necessary tools and internet access to use ChatGPT effectively.					
5	When utilizing ChatGPT, I can ask for help from other users.					
Trustworthiness						
Scale: 1. Never, 2. Rarely, 3. Sometimes, 4. Often, 5. Always						
1	I have faith that whatever I do on ChatGPT will be private and safe.					

2	I believe utilizing ChatGPT for communication would be safe enough.					
3	I believe ChatGPT would protect the confidentiality of my personal information.					
4	I am afraid of making mistakes in the process of using ChatGPT.					
5	I believe ChatGPT will be useful for organizing my studies and courses.					
Adoption of ChatGPT						
Scale: 1. Never, 2. Rarely, 3. Sometimes, 4. Often, 5. Always						
1	I intend to use the ChatGPT in my profession.					
2	I am sure to use ChatGPT to aid in my professional life.					
3	I am determined to acquire the skills to operate ChatGPT.					
4	I have a desire to increase my usage of ChatGPT.					
5	I plan to suggest ChatGPT to my colleague.					
6	I intend to use ChatGPT to answer my queries related to my profession.					